

RADIAL LOBES (line 4 o page 1)

$$|R_{7,3}(r)|^2 = \left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^9 \left(\frac{1}{84 \cdot 10!}\right) r^6 e^{-2r/7} \left[\underbrace{-\left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^3}_{a=-\left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^3} \cdot r^3 + \underbrace{30 \cdot \left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^2}_{b=30\left(\frac{2}{7}\right)^2} \cdot r^2 - \underbrace{270 \cdot \left(\frac{2}{7}\right)}_{c=-270\left(\frac{2}{7}\right)} r + \underbrace{720}_{d} \right]^2$$

MATLAB script

```
% Radial lobes
% *****
r = linspace(1,100,100);
FS = 'FontSize'; FW = 'Fontweight';
f = 2/7; 0 = f^9*(84*factorial(10))^-1;
a = -(2/7)^3;
b = 30*(2/7)^2;
c = -270*(2/7);
d = 720;
for I = 1:100
    S1 = r(I)^6*exp(-2*r(I)/7);
    S = S1*(a*r(I)^3+b*r(I)^2+c*r(I)+720)^2;
    S(I) = S^0.5
end
Imax = max(S)
plot(r,S,'r','Linewidth',2)
xlabel('Bohr radii',FS,16)
ylabel('Intensity',FS,16)
text(30,Imax/2,'R(n=7,l=3)',FS,20,FW,'bold')
```


NOTE

In order to cover the wide dynamic range of intensities in Figure 3 of the source manuscript, the intensities needed to be compressed. This was done using the intensities $I^{0.5}$ instead of I .